

ISic1093

I.Sicily inscription 1093

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mazara del Vallo, Cathedral

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR107930

1. Κάνθειε Μαρκιανὲ πᾶσι ποθινότατε

Edition: PHI140577

1. Λ[.].COIC[— — —] Μαικιανὸ [ς]²⁷Μαρκιανὸ[ς]²⁷ [— — —] πᾶσι □ πο θ,ξ
[ινὸς — δια]νοίαις [—]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284755

EDR 107930

EDCS 39102252

PHI 140577

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

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At no.36

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